

Invitation to participate in a DATA REQUEST exercise on variable prioritisation

Briony Turner [REDACTED]

Wed 13/04/2022 12:39

To: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Cc: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Dear colleagues,

Greetings from the newly established CMIP International Project Office. As part of the CMIP community, you are invited to participate in a DATA REQUEST exercise on variable prioritisation. We are supporting the WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP) to implement this activity.

If you would like to participate in this activity, please complete this form [REDACTED] before **11am UTC 21 April 2022**. This will enable you to:

- Express interest in attending an online workshop in May
- Express interest in being a paper author or reviewer
- Contribute your thoughts on methodological approach (the questions are based on reviewing [this list of parameters](#), indicating how you feel about the number prioritised, the [methodology](#) proposed, any additional quantitative criteria you feel should be taken into account in short-listing, any science/impact based prioritisation issues for consideration and any thoughts you have on alternative methodological approaches to prioritisation)

If you have any questions about this, or would like to reach out to the new CMIP IPO about anything else, please do contact myself or CMIP-IPO Director, Eleanor O'Rourke [REDACTED].

Best wishes,
Briony

HE Space for ESA - European Space Agency

Briony Turner

Programme Manager

WCRP Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) International Project Office

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PDF of application form previously linked in the email above.

CMIP DATA REQUEST variable prioritisation: Event registration, input and author Eol

CMIP has expanded and now has a substantial range of communities, all with their own specialised requirements. The WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP) are aware that there are too many variables being listed as top priority and that conflicts are emerging between what the data centres and data users (including intermediary platforms such as C3S) would consider highest priority.

The Data Request function of the WIP wish to address the immediate challenge of establishing an agreed variable prioritisation methodology from the CMIP modelling community and some means of giving authority to "priority = 1" statements; a community intention discussed at WGCM 2019 in Barcelona. It is envisaged that these prioritised variables can form a baseline set of variables for exchange of climate model data, in following FAIR data and Open Science principles. The intention is to publish these as a Geoscientific Model Development (GMD) paper.

The CMIP community are therefore invited to provide input to, and consider self-nomination for paper authorship of, a paper setting out an appropriate methodology for prioritising variables that could be considered as a baseline set of variables for exchange of climate model data, in any intercomparison project, in accordance with FAIR data and Open Science principles. There are three sections to this survey, it will take you 5-10 minutes to complete, longer if you wish to provide detailed responses.

Section 1 - Your details (required)

Section 2 - Workshop preference and EOI for paper roles (author/reviewer) (required)

Section 3 - Your thoughts on methodological approach (optional) -these will be used to underpin workshop discussions

This participation form has been developed by the CMIP International Project Office, hosted by ESA Climate Office, in consultation with the WCRP WGCM Infrastructure Panel. This workstream is being led by Martin Juckes, UKRI-STFC working alongside Charlotte Pascoe NCAS/CEDA and Alison Parent, CEDA. If you have any problems completing this form/accessing the links please contact: [REDACTED]

This participation form has been issued by CMIP IPO to the Modelling Centre leads, data request leads and the MIP Chairs and can be shared more widely if you are aware of others that would wish to input into this activity.

Please note this Registration & Author Expression of Interest form closed 18:00 UTC 26 April 2022 however you can still share your thoughts on the methodological approach and indicate which workshop you'd like to attend until 18:00 UTC 6 May 2022.

Your details

Data handling notification: Your answers in this response will be stored, reviewed and analysed by staff of the CMIP-IPO hosted by ESA Climate Office and CEDA based at STFC. Your entry to this form, subject to your inclusion consent, could be made available as part of the response data for further analysis with the paper authors, currently not yet appointed.

1. Consent for workshop report inclusion *

- I am happy to have my name, prefix, affiliation and institution recorded in a workshop report which could form an annex to the paper based on the responses to this form. (we will reconfirm with you once the paper is ready and you can review the context of inclusion).
- No, please keep my response as anonymous

2. Prefix *

- Dr
- Professor
- Please leave as blank
- Other

3. **Name (Forename Surname) ***

4. **Institution (Please write out in full) ***

5. **Country institution is based in**

6. **Email address ***

7. **CMIP involvement (select as many as apply) ***

- Data Request lead
- Modelling Centre lead
- MIP Chair
- Other

8. If you selected 'other' please list your CMIP involvement

Workshop preference and expression of interest

We invite you to participate in a two hour workshop to inform the authors' approach to identifying the parameters, structuring the paper, and identifying interested authors.

The workshop will consist of presentations, breakout groups and plenary discussion. It will include recording of points via an online collaboration platform.

- o The first set of breakout groups will be thematic; on surface, atmosphere, and ocean variables.
- o The focus of plenary discussions will be on methodological approach, paper structure and identification of authors.

For those that cannot attend either workshop but would like to participate, a recording of the first workshop will be made available with instructions for participation through the collaboration platform.

9. Would you like to express interest in being a paper author/reviewer?

- Yes -reviewer
- Yes - author
- Yes - happy to be considered for both
- No

10. If you indicated yes for consideration as a paper author, please indicate the level of involvement you are able to offer during this paper writing period (May - November) and set out the dates of any periods during this time you will not be available to work.

It is anticipated there will be meetings in the first weeks of June, July, October and November. If needed a meeting will be held in August.

11. Workshop preference *

The workshop will be held online

- Workshop 1 12 May 14:30-16:30 UTC
- Workshop 2 17 May 07:00-09:00 UTC
- I cannot attend any of these but would like to participate via Workshop #1 recording and comment form W/C 16 May
- I do not wish to participate in the workshop

12. Workshop breakout room preference for those able to attend a workshop -please indicate which breakout room(s) you would be interested in attending.

	Ocean variables	Surface variables
First choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Second choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Third choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

13. Online platforms

Please let us know if you are unable to access any of the following platforms: Microsoft Teams, Zoom, MIRO, MURAL, SLIDO, Google tools such as Jamboard/document/sheet/map

14. Accessibility requirements

Please let us know if you have any requirements/if any of the online platforms listed above are not compatible with assistive technology(ies) you use.

Your thoughts on methodological approach

This section is optional. Answers will be used to inform workshop structure and for pre-population workshop materials. Answers might also be used within a workshop report which could be used as an annex to the paper.

15. This section is optional, do you wish to comment on the proposed methodological approach/suggest alternatives? *

- Yes
- No -please take me to the end of this form

16. Please review the list of parameters available here:

<https://bit.ly/MIPVariables> [opens in new tab]. For inclusion in the 'priority 1' list , do you feel 120 is:

- Too many
- The right amount
- Too few

17. If you have any further thoughts to share on the number of parameters in the list, please do so here:

18. Please review the methodological approach described in this document here: <https://bit.ly/MIPVarMethodology>. [opens in new tab]. Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the approach:

- I strongly agree with this approach
- I agree in principle with this approach but have some reservations
- I disagree with this approach

19. Please share the reasoning for your response

20. Are there **additional quantitative** objective criteria that should be taken into account in the short listing, in addition to download volumes, download file count and degree of participation of modelling centres?

21. Are there **science/impact based** prioritisation issues which should be taken into account?

22. If you have any thoughts on **alternative methodological approaches** to prioritisation you'd like to share, please do so here.

Thank you from the CMIP-IPO

Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey. We are newly established and would welcome any thoughts you have on how we could assist in communication and coordination of the CMIP community, within the wider WCRP landscape and with users along the data supply chain.

23. Please share any thoughts/requests you have relating to the role of the CMIP-IPO

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